

IMPROVEMENT OF ACTUATED BALL VALVE IN MAIN GAS PIPELINES**Ibayeva L.***Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University**Department of Industrial machines**Phd scholar***ABSTRACT**

Ball valves are widely used in the industry, and at the same time, as one of the main nodes of fountain fittings and drilling operation manifolds included in the oilfield equipment complex, they are designed to direct or regulate the flow of liquid and gas, and to prevent the flow of liquid. In different types of faucets, sealing elements are used to ensure the sealing between the metal-metal surface, to break the connection between the plug and the cover, and to ensure hermeticity in the socket of the plug. It has been proposed to increase the longevity of the conditioner by reducing the contact voltage while maintaining the cooling effect.

Keywords: ball valve, oil and gas industry, body.

The oil and gas industry uses a wide variety of cranes to ensure the safe and efficient transportation of hydrocarbon resources. Ball valves have become a versatile and reliable choice due to their unique design and performance.

Ball valves belong to the class of 90° swivel type coupling devices. Ball valves are safe, reliable, and distinguished by their high endurance and high precision operation when not in use for a long time. Ball valves are widely used in the industry, and at the same time, as one of the main nodes of fountain fittings and drilling operation manifolds included in the oilfield equipment complex, they are designed to direct or regulate the flow of liquid and gas, and to prevent the flow of liquid.

The easy handling and reparability of ball valves have led to their widespread use in industry. Depending on the design and material, spherical horns can work at a pressure of 100 Mpa and a temperature of 400 °C. They can be made up to 48 inches in size.

The body of spherical faucets is made of metal, plastic and metal-ceramic. The blade itself is covered with a chrome coating to increase its durability.

In different types of faucets, sealing elements are used to ensure the sealing between the metal-metal surface, to break the connection between the plug and the

cover, and to ensure hermeticity in the socket of the plug. Thus, the conditioning elements are one of the main elements of the cranes, and they have a role in ensuring its efficiency.

The main issue in molding systems is the definition of criteria, which should be selected parameters that perform the required technical functions of these molding details. The required contact stress or deformation must be created in the two important contact zones of the metal-metal zone, i.e., molded with highly elastic materials (curing agents), so that the hermeticity of the joint is satisfied.

In order to create a hermetic seal according to the required characteristics (pressure, temperature, speed, etc.), in the contact zone, a deformation level must be created in the elastic molding material, so that the contact stress at that moment and for the duration of the work process maintains the stress within the required limit. Here, the first issue is the study of the process of elasticity, and the second is the process of relaxation stresses. For this purpose, the main direction of the issue is the study of the functionality of the structural potentials of the connectors that satisfy the given requirements.

Picture 1. Actuated ball valve

Picture 2. 1-body, 2-flange, 3-saddle, 4-ball, 5-spring, 6-spindle, 7-bolt, 8- nut, 9-top cover, 10-cuff, 11-bottom cover, 12-washer

Picture 3. Spherical ball valves

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Problems and innovations in the technology of ball valves

A. Solving problems related to high pressure and high temperature.

Innovations in valve materials, molding and construction allow ball valves to withstand extreme pressures and temperatures in complex oil and gas environments.

B. Resistance to corrosion and erosion.

Modern materials and coatings increase the service life and reliability of ball valves, increasing their resistance to corrosion and erosion.

C. Improvement of molding technology

The use of soft and hard saddles, as well as improved molding structures, improve the characteristics of ball valves, reducing the risks of leakage and ejection.

D. Development of intelligent taps and remote monitoring system

The integration of intelligent technologies such as sensors, transmissions and communication systems enables remote monitoring and control of ball valves, increasing operational efficiency and safety. Ball valves have a number of advantages that allow them to be used for various purposes in the oil and gas industry:

1. High conductivity

Spherical valves are ideal for use in the oil and gas industry due to their full-flow construction and the ability to release loads even at small pressure drops. This shows that operations can be carried out with high efficiency.

2. Sharp and simple work.

We now know that we can quickly open and close ball valves by turning the ball valve support or actuator 90°, making them useful for controlling the process quickly and efficiently. This quick operation also reduces any possible leaks and other problems that may occur in the long-term operation of the faucet.

3. Low operating costs

Due to their simple and robust construction, ball valves require minimal maintenance. They are less prone to corrosion, which ensures long-term service and reduces downtime during maintenance.

4. Compact closure

Ball valves provide a hermetic seal due to the fact that the ball and saddle have a special construction that prevents any leakage when the valve is closed. Even if corrosion or fire melts the soft seat of the ball valve, the special flexible compensation structure adheres to the steel of the floating ball valve, performing a tight shear function. This is especially important in the oil and gas sector, where stopping leaks is critical to meeting safety and environmental protection standards.

5. Wide selection of materials

Ball valves are suitable for a wide range of applications under high pressure, high temperature and corrosion conditions in the oil and gas field. The material of the body can be made of various materials, stainless steel, carbon, alloy steel, which makes them universal for use in the oil and gas industry.

Picture 4. Ball valve with reduced bore

Conclusion

During the operation of spherical cranes, in order to ensure the stability of the stabilizers, it was proposed to increase the longevity of the stabilizer by reducing the contact voltage while maintaining the shear effect.

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